

**BUILDING BASIC CONSIDERING APTITUDES IS THE PREMISE OF
MAKING STRIDES MENTAL CAPACITY**

Abstract. This article talks about pedagogical considerations aimed at forming critical thinking skills, the essence of critical thinking. Ways to improve intellectual ability through the formation of critical thinking skills are widely described.

Keywords: critical thinking, reflective thinking, critical thinking, thinking about thinking, conceptualization, cognitive thinking.

Introduction

In today's globalized environment, it is up to the new generation with independent thinking and critical thinking skills to solve the pressing problems of society's development. We imagine a thought that changes depending on the situation. A child gets into a certain situation and immediately begins to observe, analyze, process information, draw conclusions, make decisions, and take responsibility. This is critical thinking. Critical thinking is a system of thinking that is used to analyze things and events with reasonable conclusions and allows rational evaluation and interpretation, as well as the application of the obtained results to situations and problems. Critical thinking is what to believe or how to act. effective, reflective thinking aimed at making decisions about what to do. Also, critical thinking is the ability to question the information being studied, including one's own judgments, also known as "Thinking About Thinking". One of the most common definitions is "rational reflexive thinking aimed at deciding what to believe and what to do," the active and skillful analysis, observation, experience, and communication of information received or generated as a point of reference for conviction and action. is conceptualized as, an intellectually regulated process of application, synthesis, or evaluation [1].

The term "critical thinking" itself goes back to the philosopher John Dewey. He used the term more as 'reflective thinking': 'the active, consistent and careful consideration of any thought or assumed form of knowledge in terms of the grounds that support it and its implications'. According to the scientist J. Devi: "students develop critical thinking only when they begin to deal with a specific problem. Therefore, the most important question about the situation or event, which is considered the starting point of the learning process, is the question of what kind of problem this event creates. cries. In fact, it is necessary to determine the level of independent thinking of students during the educational process. Because critical thinking is a component of independent thinking. To define more

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clearly what critical thinking is, Richard Paul (1995) proposed to divide critical thinking into strong and weak types. He describes weak critical thinking as the selfish thinking of a highly qualified but self-interested pseudo-intellectual who does not seriously consider the moral consequences of his actions. they use their knowledge to achieve unfair and selfish goals. In addition, critical thinking is characterized by making logical inferences, creating coherent logical models, and making informed decisions about rejecting, agreeing, or temporarily deferring judgment [3]. All these definitions refer to mental activity that should be directed to solving a specific cognitive task.

Key skills required for critical thinking include observation, interpretation, analysis, inference, and evaluation. Critical thinking uses logic, but also relies on it. In our opinion, critical thinking is a high-level component of knowledge acquisition and independent thinking, and it is a mental phenomenon that expands a person's ability to objectively perceive events, phenomena and existence. In critical thinking, ideas and their significance are examined from multiple perspectives and compared to other ideas. Emphasis is placed on analysis, comparison, interpretation, innovation, problem solving, and students believe that creative ideas triumph over evil ideas. "Critical thinking is a type of thinking that requires people to reflect and consider the decisions that shape their thoughts and actions. "Critical thinking allows people to think logically, process complex information, and consider different aspects of a problem, then they can draw firm conclusions [4]. "Critical thinking is the seven disciplines of curiosity, openness to different aspects, ability to think systematically, analytical approach, persistence in reality, self-confidence to think critically and finally maturity. Although critical thinking can be defined in different ways, its there is general agreement that the main ingredient is the desire to achieve a satisfactory result, and this should be achieved through rational thinking and results-oriented work. During the process of working in small groups, students behave more freely. Even by giving wrong answers, children who are afraid of embarrassment will also have the opportunity to demonstrate their knowledge. They will see that their opinions are valued by others. Shy students in the class will be active. Working in a group will give him a sense of self-confidence. Consists of 4-5 students a shy student in a group will feel more free than answering in front of 30-35 students. In general, working in small groups teaches teachers and students to be more active, to feel responsible for the group, and to improve their communication skills. helps to develop. This, in turn, requires the wide use of innovative methods that help individual pupils and students gain interest in the lesson, develop their independence and activity, and develop critical thinking.

Therefore, the comprehensive development of New Uzbekistan and the success of the implemented reforms depend on the level of formation of independent thinking, broad knowledge, education and general culture of the young generation. Therefore, it is a social need to form the skills of free observation and critical thinking in all young people in our society. First of all,

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students should be taught that they are responsible for critical thinking. A teacher's job is to create an environment that encourages critical thinking. Critical thinking is a complex process of thinking that begins with assimilation of information and ends with a conclusion. However, critical thinking is a pedagogical technology aimed at developing the ability of students to work with a text, acquire oral and written speech, and act together with peers in this text as a higher level of cognitive activity. Critical thinking is a set of strategies that can change the mindset of the learning process, that is, the lesson becomes the creation of the teacher and the students. Structures of critical thinking, specific features of individual components that determine methods of forming generalized methods of mental activity are analyzed. In these studies, preparation for systematic education and all-round activation of the individual has been developed based on directing elementary school students to acquire all components of critical thinking. The realization of these goals as a complete concept requires the need to improve all links of traditional didactic systems, including motives, methods and organizational means of forming active critical thinking of students and its in-depth research at different age stages of human development.

In conclusion, it should be said that critical thinking has a positive effect on the intellectual skills and development of the student. Critical thinking requires a lot of focus and conscious thought work. When a critical thinking approach is applied to learning, it helps the student's mind to work better and understand the texts in a different way. Different areas of learning may require different types of critical thinking. Critical thinking provides multiple perspectives and perspectives on the same material. Without freedom and knowledge, there is no critical thinking. Any society needs an educated generation with critical thinking skills. Critical thinking is the basis of discoveries, the main driver of innovation and the pillar of social development.

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